

¹ **Memory properties in cloud-resolving simulations of**
² **the diurnal cycle of deep convection**

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3 **Abstract.** A series of high-resolution three-dimensional simulations of
4 the diurnal cycle of deep convection over land are performed using the new
5 Met Office NERC cloud-resolving model. This study features scattered con-
6 vection. A memory function is defined to identify the effects of previous con-
7 vection in modifying current convection. It is based on the probability of find-
8 ing rain at time t_0 and at an earlier time $t_0 - \Delta t$ compared to the expected
9 probability given no memory. The memory is examined as a function of the
10 lag time Δt . It is strongest at grey-zone scales of 4–10 km, there is a change
11 of behaviour for spatial scales between 10–15 km, and it is reduced substan-
12 tially for spatial scales larger than 25 km. At grey-zone scales, there is a first
13 phase of the memory function which represents the persistence of convec-
14 tion and it is maintained for about an hour. There is a second phase which
15 represents the suppression of convection in regions which were raining 1 to
16 3 hours previously, and subsequently a third phase which represents a sec-
17 ondary enhancement of precipitation. The second and third phases of the
18 memory function develop earlier for weaker forcing.

19 When thermodynamic fluctuations resulting from the previous day are al-
20 lowed to influence the development of convection on the next day, there are
21 fewer rainfall events with relatively large sizes, which are more intense and
22 thus, decay and recover more slowly, in comparison to the simulations where
23 feedback from previous days is removed. Further sensitivity experiments re-
24 veal that convective memory attributed to these thermodynamic fluctuations
25 resides in the lower troposphere.

Plain Language Summary

26 Identifying the effects of previous convection in modifying the subsequent
27 development of convection is important for correctly capturing the large-scale
28 effects of moist convection (convective parameterization) in numerical mod-
29 els used for weather forecasts and climate prediction. We evaluate these mem-
30 ory effects from idealized cloud resolving model simulations of the diurnal
31 cycle of scattered convection. We find that the main convective systems per-
32 sist for about an hour. Later convection is suppressed in those regions which
33 were raining 1 to 3 hours previously, and later still there is a secondary en-
34 hancement of convection in the regions that were previously suppressed. These
35 memory effects are sensitive to the size of the region over which they are eval-
36 uated: they are small for length scales coarser than 50 km but become in-
37 creasingly important at scales of 10 km or less. At these finer scales they are
38 inconsistent with the diagnostic assumptions made in many current convec-
39 tive parameterization schemes.

40 We also investigated the effects of the previous days convective activity
41 on that of the next day, in particular through the effects on spatial variabil-
42 ity of temperature and moisture in the lower troposphere. If the variability
43 associated with the previous day is artificially removed, then the convective
44 systems become numerous but less intense. They are found to be smaller and
45 to decay more rapidly, with a more rapid recovery of the atmosphere in their
46 vicinity.

1. Introduction

47 Tropical convection provides the most important source of energy for the global-scale
48 atmospheric flow. Over land, it is observed to undergo strong diurnal variation in intensity,
49 with rainfall peaking in the late afternoon or evening [e.g., *Lin et al.*, 2000; *Yang and*
50 *Slingo*, 2001]. This diurnal variation of convection plays a key role in the global climate
51 system since the resulting clouds and precipitation strongly modulate the atmospheric
52 radiative budget, water budget, and surface fluxes. The diurnal cycle is strongly coupled to
53 physical processes parameterized in General Circulation Models (GCMs). These include,
54 boundary layer heating, surface heat exchange, cloud–radiation interactions, often the
55 convection itself. Therefore, it is necessary to predict correctly the phasing of convection
56 with solar radiation in order to get an accurate radiation budget, and the ability of GCMs
57 to capture the correct phasing is an important test of model parameterizations.

58 Despite the improvement in the parameterization of model physical processes made
59 over the past decade, current state-of-art GCMs still have difficulty to capture the broad
60 pattern of the diurnal variation of convection, in terms of intensity and phase [e.g., *Yang*
61 *and Slingo*, 2001; *Betts and Jakob*, 2002; *Bechtold et al.*, 2004; *Lee et al.*, 2008; *Hohenegger*
62 *et al.*, 2013]. In particular, GCMs that capture the intensity of the diurnal cycle tend to
63 produce an onset of precipitation early in the day compared to observations [e.g., *Lin*
64 *et al.*, 2000; *Yang and Slingo*, 2001; *Betts and Jakob*, 2002; *Bechtold et al.*, 2004]. The
65 superparameterization approach [e.g., *Grabowski*, 2001; *Khairoutdinov and Randall*, 2001;
66 *Khairoutdinov et al.*, 2005] has been demonstrated to improve the simulated diurnal cycle
67 of precipitation. However, the integrations are computationally expensive. Some recent

68 studies have improved the representation of convection using different approaches and
69 produced some improvements in the diurnal cycle representation. Approaches include
70 modifications to the closure [*Bechtold et al.*, 2014] or entrainment [*Stratton and Stirling*,
71 2012], a representation of the control of convection by boundary layer thermals and cold
72 pools [*Rio et al.*, 2013], and a unification of shallow and deep convection including both
73 cold pool and mesoscale representations [*Park et al.*, 2019].

74 The difficulties of GCMs in predicting the diurnal cycle suggest that parameterizations
75 respond too quickly to surface forcing. *Colin et al.* [2019] provide a good description
76 of the main issues in this regard. Convection schemes generally focus on relatively large
77 spatial scales and make the “quasi equilibrium” assumption [*Arakawa and Schubert*, 1974;
78 *Arakawa*, 2004; *Yano and Plant*, 2012a]; that convection balances the large-scale forcing.
79 Most convection schemes also involve a separate “triggering” formulation, and diagnose
80 whether a triggering variable satisfies particular conditions before determining the closure
81 variable that governs how convection responds to the large-scale forcing. The key point
82 stressed by *Colin et al.* [2019] is that both the triggering and closure are usually treated as
83 diagnostic [subsections 5b and 5c in *Arakawa*, 2004] so that the parameterized convective
84 effects depend only on state variables at the grid-scale and at the same time. However,
85 these diagnostic assumptions become increasingly questionable as progress is being made
86 towards running GCMs with higher-resolution and shorter time steps.

87 Following *Davies et al.* [2009] and *Colin et al.* [2019], we refer to “memory” as being the
88 information that needs to be retained about previous convection in order to determine
89 the characteristics of current convection. Various authors have attempted to introduce
90 elements of memory into convection parameterizations [e.g., *Chen and Bougeault*, 1992;

91 *Randall and Pan*, 1993; *Grandpeix and Lafore*, 2010; *Yano and Plant*, 2012b; *Park*, 2014;
92 *Rio et al.*, 2019]. However, as *Colin et al.* [2019] recognized, there is little consistency
93 within these and other approaches in terms of the variables that are chosen to be prog-
94 nostic, or relatedly, the assumed physical origins for the memory mechanism. This study
95 seeks to bring new insights on the relationship between convection and its own history.

96 There are several well-documented cases of idealized diurnal cycles. For instance, in the
97 European Cloud Systems (EUROCS) Project case study, *Guichard et al.* [2004] presented
98 a series of CRM and SCM results from multi-day simulations of the diurnally varying con-
99 vection over one of the Atmospheric Radiation Measurement (ARM) sites centered over
100 the Southern Great Plains (SGP), USA, during summer 1997. Other intercomparison
101 studies that have been helpful in this respect include the CRMs and SCMs simulations of
102 the diurnal cycle that were performed within the Global Energy and Water-cycle Exper-
103 iment (GEWEX) cloud system study (GCSS) Working Group 4 Case 3 framework [e.g.,
104 *Xu et al.*, 2002; *Xie et al.*, 2002].

105 *Stirling and Petch* [2004] investigated the impact of spatial variability generated via
106 feedback processes from previous convection on current development of convection. They
107 demonstrated that the onset of precipitation and total rain amount can change signifi-
108 cantly if internally generated thermodynamic variability from a day of deep convection
109 is included in the initial thermodynamic conditions. This suggests that the presence of
110 spatial variability in the initial thermodynamic conditions pre-conditions the atmosphere,
111 influences the subsequent development of convection, and thus provides a mechanism for
112 memory. Further investigations have provided more evidence that convective memory
113 is carried by thermodynamic variability [*Davies et al.*, 2013; *Colin et al.*, 2019]. Other

114 possible sources identified for memory include free tropospheric moisture variations [e.g.,
115 *Dudhia et al.*, 1987; *Redelsperger et al.*, 2002], cold pools and gust fronts due to evap-
116 oration of precipitation [e.g., *Mapes and Houze*, 1992; *Tompkins*, 2001], drylines [e.g.,
117 *Bluestein and Parker*, 1993], and horizontal convective rolls [e.g., *Weckwerth et al.*, 1996].
118 *Davies et al.* [2013] focused on memory for different periods of imposed forcing while
119 [*Colin et al.*, 2019] focused on the effects of organization on memory. Here, we investigate
120 disorganized convection with an imposed diurnal forcing timescale and focus on evaluating
121 how memory can be characterized for different length scales, and its dependence on the
122 chosen forcing strength. Results from the new Met Office NERC cloud model (MONC;
123 *Brown et al.* [2015]) simulations of the diurnal cycle of deep convection over land will
124 be presented. The simulated case is an idealization of the EUROCS diurnal-cycle deep-
125 convection case study [*Guichard et al.*, 2004]. Specifications of the EUROCS case study
126 along with the results from several CRMs and SCMs are described in *Bechtold et al.*
127 [2004]. Another major focus of this study will be on assessing the impacts that thermody-
128 namic variability generated at night after decaying deep convection has on the next day's
129 convective development. We will determine the timescale and length scale within which
130 convective memory is effective.

2. Model description and simulation setup

2.1. The new Met Office NERC Cloud Model

131 The CRM used in this study is the new Met Office NERC cloud model (MONC; *Brown*
132 *et al.* [2015]) which is a rewrite of the original Met Office Large-Eddy Model (LEM). The
133 original Met Office LEM [as described by *Shutts and Gray*, 1994; *Petch and Gray*, 2001]
134 has been successfully exploited for modelling convective and cloud related processes in a

135 variety of regimes [e.g., *Brown*, 1999; *Brown et al.*, 2002; *Clark et al.*, 2005; *Connolly et*
136 *al.*, 2006, 2013; *Marsham et al.*, 2006; *Young et al.*, 2017]. It has been rewritten to include
137 a new solver that enables simulations to be performed with relatively large domain sizes
138 without having to compromise on model resolution. Other improvements include bug fixes
139 and code optimizations. The reader is referred to *Brown et al.* [2015] for further details.

140 Cloud processes are simulated using the newly-developed user-configurable Cloud
141 AeroSol Interactive Microphysics (CASIM) scheme. CASIM is a multi-moment scheme
142 that represents five hydrometeor species; cloud water, rain, ice, snow, and graupel. In
143 this study, CASIM represents each of those species using prognostic variables for both the
144 mixing ratios and number concentrations. Autoconversion and accretion are represented
145 using the scheme developed by *Khairoutdinov and Kogan* [2000] and the sedimentation of
146 the five hydrometeor species is also represented. Condensation and evaporation of cloud
147 droplets are represented using a saturation adjustment scheme, while rain evaporation is
148 represented as in the LEM [*Gray et al.*, 2001]. CASIM has recently been used to study the
149 role of droplet sedimentation in the evolution of low-level clouds in MONC [e.g., *Dearden*
150 *et al.*, 2018]. It has also been configured for multi-mode aerosols to study aerosol-cloud
151 interactions in the UK Met Office Unified Model [e.g., *Grosvenor et al.*, 2017; *Miltenberger*
152 *et al.*, 2018; *Stevens et al.*, 2018].

2.2. Simulation Settings

153 The horizontal domain size is 512×512 grid points and the horizontal resolution is 200
154 m. The vertical grid consists of 99 levels, on a stretched grid with finer resolution closer to
155 the surface. The vertical grid spacing is stretched from 35 m near the surface to 250 m in
156 the upper troposphere (12 km), and increasing to 450 m near the model top, which is at

157 20 km. The lateral boundary conditions are bi-periodic for all prognostic variables. The
158 top and bottom of the domain are rigid lids and a Newtonian damping layer is used aloft
159 (from 15 km to 20 km). A 3D Smagorinsky scheme is used to calculate subgrid turbulent
160 eddy fluxes. The Coriolis parameter is set to zero and the horizontal mean winds are
161 relaxed toward zero with a relaxation timescale of 1 hour.

162 For the purposes of this study, we focus on the atmospheric variability controlling mem-
163 ory, and so to separate that out from that resulting from the surface properties, we choose
164 not to couple the model to an interactive land surface. For the control simulation the sur-
165 face specification closely follows the EUROCS diurnal-cycle deep-convection case study
166 [*Guichard et al.*, 2004]. The model is forced with prescribed horizontally homogeneous
167 surface forcing which vary sinusoidally during the day (0–12 h) and are set to zero at
168 night (12–24 h). The peaks in sensible and latent heat fluxes are reached at 6 h and they
169 are 130 and 400 W m⁻², respectively.

170 The model is forced with a net atmospheric radiation term that represents the combined
171 effects of shortwave and longwave radiation. It is horizontally homogeneous and non-
172 interactive and will be referred to as radiative cooling. The cooling is applied to potential
173 temperature. It has a constant value of -1.75 K day⁻¹ from the surface to 12 km and
174 decreasing linearly in height to reach 0 K day⁻¹ at 15 km. During the night (12–24 h),
175 an additional cooling of -3.1 K day⁻¹ is applied at the surface decreasing linearly to
176 zero at 1 km. These idealized cooling profiles (day and night) are designed to balance
177 the prescribed time-varying surface fluxes over a 24-hour period (complete forcing cycle),
178 so that the simulations remain energetically closed in terms of the moist static energy
179 budget. The additional cooling rate applied at night approximately matches the mean

180 radiative cooling in the lowest 1 km at night in an equivalent simulation of the diurnal
181 cycle of convection using the idealised setup of the UK Met Office Unified Model with the
182 same settings but with interactive radiation (not shown). In this study, it is applied in
183 order to produce a stable boundary layer at dawn and thus, to delay the triggering and
184 onset of precipitation on the next diurnal cycle.

185 To investigate the sensitivity to the strength of forcing, we also performed weakly and
186 strongly forced simulations. The Bowen ratio is the same as in the control simulation,
187 but, the values of sensible and latent heat fluxes, and the values of radiative cooling rates
188 are reduced by 50% in the weakly forced simulation and increased by 50% in the strongly
189 forced simulation. To ensure statistically significant results, all three simulations are run
190 for ten successive diurnal cycles.

3. Evaluation of convective properties over time-varying surface forcing

3.1. Evaluation over one complete forcing cycle

191 Analysis of the control simulation in terms of convective stability and boundary layer
192 height has shown that the model is able to reproduce a diurnal cycle of these parameters
193 (not shown). Figure 1 shows the time-height cross sections of the domain average mass
194 flux (ρw) and cloud fraction (σ) for the control simulation. Here, we show the mass flux
195 and cloud fraction of two conditional sampled diagnostics: all cloudy updrafts (“ACu”;
196 shading) and buoyant cloudy updrafts or cloud cores (“BCu”; contours). All cloudy
197 updrafts are defined by grid points with mixing ratio of liquid cloud (q_l) or ice (q_i) greater
198 than 10^{-5} kg kg $^{-1}$ and positive vertical velocity ($w > 0$), while cloud cores are defined as
199 cloudy updraft points which are also positively buoyant with respect to the layer-mean
200 ($\theta'_v > 0$ K). Here, the fractional area attributed to “BCu” (or “ACu”) is calculated at each

201 horizontal level as the sum of cloudy updrafts (or buoyant cloudy updrafts) grid points
202 normalized by the total number of grid points. Results in Figure 1 are shown for the
203 second diurnal cycle of the control simulation, but are similar for the nine diurnal cycles
204 used in our analysis.

205 The initial response of convection, termed “triggering” corresponds to the development
206 of shallow convection at the top of the boundary layer. In the control simulation the
207 triggering starts at approximately 2.75 h and convection develops rapidly through the
208 troposphere. Deep cloud tops reach levels as high as 12 km at 4 h (1.25 hours after
209 triggering), then emerge further and reach the maximum level of about 14 km at 7.75 h.
210 The cloud base rises slowly through the day, consistent with the warming and deepening
211 of the sub-cloud layer.

212 Cloud fractions show a bimodal distributions. The first mode centered at about 1.5 km
213 is due to shallow convection, while the second, broadest, mode which extends from 6 to
214 14 km results from intermediate and deep convection. These profiles of cloud fractions
215 broadly agree with those obtained in previous studies of this nature [e.g., *Xu et al.*, 2002;
216 *Xie et al.*, 2002; *Guichard et al.*, 2004].

217 In the lower and middle troposphere convection starts to weaken gradually shortly after
218 4 h. As a result, liquid clouds forming below the freezing level located at about 5 km
219 decay accordingly and vanish completely as convection stops. In the upper troposphere
220 the largest cloud fractions occur shortly after 5 h. As the lower and middle tropospheric
221 clouds decay, the upper tropospheric clouds dominate the skies. These clouds decay more
222 slowly and vanish completely at 15 h, that is about 2 h after the mass flux has decayed in
223 the upper troposphere. Between 15–24 h the column is free from convection and cloud.

224 The free tropospheric cooling rate applied in the control simulation is weaker than the
225 value of about -2 K day^{-1} applied in previous studies of the diurnal cycle of convection
226 with similar values of surface forcing [e.g., *Xu et al.*, 2002; *Stirling and Petch*, 2004]. In
227 preliminary simulations with -2 K day^{-1} cooling rate, we found that condensation (upper
228 level anvils and/or low level clouds) and sometimes convection were generated between
229 15–24 h and before triggering on the next diurnal cycle (not shown). As the air becomes
230 colder at night, condensation can occur, and the latent heat released can trigger convective
231 activity. The stronger the cooling rate in the free troposphere, the quicker the air cools
232 below its dew point value and in the control simulation a cooling rate smaller or equal
233 to -1.75 K day^{-1} is required to ensure that no regions of saturation are formed between
234 15–24 h and before triggering on the next diurnal cycle. However, as we will discuss in
235 section 3.2.2, choosing a different radiative cooling profile does not significantly change
236 the memory function that illustrates the dependence of convection on its own history.

237 We analyzed the time-height cross sections of the spatially averaged mass flux and
238 cloud fraction for the weakly and strongly forced simulations (not shown). The weakly
239 forced simulation is free from convection and clouds between 15–24 h and the triggering
240 is at 3.25 h. In the strongly forced simulation the triggering is at 2.5 h but clouds occur
241 from 20 h to a couple of hours after the start of surface forcing on the next forcing
242 cycle as a result of condensation from radiative cooling over night. Analysis reveals
243 that these clouds are generated within two thin layers; at the top of the boundary layer
244 (associated with light precipitation) and around the freezing level. However, in all three
245 simulations the triggering corresponds to a rapid intensification of convection and the rates
246 of growth of cloud tops are very similar, with cloud tops exceeding 10 km one hour after

247 triggering. Analysis of the horizontal cross sections of clouds also reveals that convection
248 is disorganized in all three simulations.

3.2. Evaluation over multiple forcing cycles

249 We now discuss the characteristics of the ensemble over multiple forcing cycles. For
250 each of the three simulations, the last nine cycles are considered to form an ensemble of
251 simulations of the diurnal cycle differentiated by the initial conditions. The end of the
252 diurnal cycle $i - 1$ provides starting conditions for the cycle i . The start of each of the
253 nine cycles is considered to be time 0 and ensemble-mean results are obtained.

254 Figure 2 shows the composite timeseries of surface precipitation rates, mass flux and
255 cloud fraction attributed to all cloudy updrafts and buoyant cloudy updrafts at cloud
256 base. Here, the cloud base height is defined as the lowest point in the domain where q_l
257 $> 10^{-5} \text{ kg kg}^{-1}$. Results are shown for the nine control simulations and the shaded areas
258 represent the standard deviation from the ensemble-mean of each quantity, which is used
259 to quantify the cycle-to-cycle fluctuations relative to the ensemble-mean.

260 The time of triggering is defined as the time just before the sharp increase of cloud base
261 mass flux occurs. It is at approximately 2.75 h and the rapid intensification of convection
262 with deep convective cloud top emerging rapidly into the upper troposphere and sharp
263 increase in surface precipitation rates are common to each cycle. The peak in precipitation
264 is at 4.5 h (1.75 hours after triggering). Cloud fraction and mass flux at cloud base reach
265 their maximum values at 3.75 h, then adjust rapidly to much smaller values. From 4.5 h,
266 surface precipitation, cloud base mass flux, and cloud fraction continue to decrease until
267 shortly after the surface forcing is switched off.

268 The details of the evolution of the convection (e.g., timing and values of precipitation,
269 mass flux, and cloud fraction) vary from one forcing cycle to the other but overall, the
270 composite timeseries of precipitation shows a greater variability than those of mass flux
271 and cloud fraction. Between 3–11 h, the fractional area covered by cloud cores represents
272 about 60% of that of all cloudy updrafts. However, the values of mass flux are very close
273 for the two definitions, suggesting that cloud cores are the dominant source of mass flux.

274 Figures 3 a and b show the composite timeseries of the normalized precipitation and
275 the cloud base mass flux, respectively for different forcing strengths. The normalized
276 precipitation is defined as the instantaneous precipitation rates divided by the domain–
277 mean daily–mean precipitation rate. The domain–mean and daily–mean precipitation rate
278 is about 0.2 mm h^{-1} in the control simulation, and it is reduced (increased) by 50% in the
279 weakly (strongly) forced simulation, consistent with the strength of forcing (section 2.2).

280 As discussed in section 3.1 the triggering is delayed with decreasing strength of forcing.
281 The time of triggering is at 2.5 h in the strongly forced simulation, 2.75 h in the control
282 simulation, and 3.25 h in the weakly forced simulation. Figures 3 c and d show the same
283 results as in 3 a and b but the time axis is shifted such that time equals 0 corresponds
284 to the time of triggering in all three simulations. Convection is more active (in terms of
285 mass flux) as the strength of forcing is increased. However, the normalized precipitation is
286 seen to evolve at very similar rates, reaching its peak at 1.75 (in the control and strongly
287 forced simulations) or 2 (in the weakly forced simulation) hours after triggering.

288 **3.2.1. Rainfall distribution**

289 In this section, we examine the evolution of the rainfall population using instantaneous
290 2D surface precipitation fields output every 15 minutes. By adopting a precipitation

291 threshold of 0.1 mm h^{-1} in all three simulations (that is 50% of the domain-mean daily-
 292 mean surface precipitation rate in the control simulation), any grid point with precipita-
 293 tion greater than that threshold is masked as rainy. A simple algorithm is then applied
 294 to classify the resulting 2D masked field into clusters or rainfall events. We will refer to
 295 these rainfall events as rain cores and in the rest of text, rain cores and rainfall events
 296 will be used interchangeably. Starting from any rainy grid point a cluster i is formed
 297 by connecting rainy points in the x and y directions. The area of the cluster i is then
 298 computed as $A_i = n_i \Delta x \Delta y$ where n_i is the number of rainy grid points that belong to
 299 that cluster and Δx and Δy are the horizontal grid spacings in the x and y directions,
 300 respectively. The number of rain cores, N , is the total number of clusters and the mean
 301 rain core area, \bar{A} , is:

$$\bar{A} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N A_i \quad (1)$$

303 Figure 4 a presents the composite of rain core area probability distribution functions
 304 (PDFs). Results are the average of PDFs between $[0.25-0.75]$, $[1-1.25]$, $[1.5-1.75]$, $[2-2.5]$,
 305 $[2.75-6.5]$, and $[6.75-9.5]$ hours after triggering in the control simulation. The majority
 306 of rainfall events produced within the first hour after triggering are less than 4 km^2 . As
 307 time progresses, larger rainfall events are produced, resulting in a broadening of rain core
 308 area distribution. The distributions between hours 2.5–9.5 are very similar. They are
 309 relatively broad, with many small rainfall events ($A_i < 10 \text{ km}^2$) as well as some large
 310 ones. Thus, a simple mean rain core radius may not be sufficient to assess the evolution
 311 of the rainfall populations; a rain core radius standard deviation, σ_R is also useful.

312 By assuming that rainfall population consists mostly of events with more or less round
 313 shapes, the mean rain core radius, \bar{R} , is estimated as:

$$314 \quad \bar{R} = \sqrt{\frac{\bar{A}}{\pi}}. \quad (2)$$

315 The composite timeseries of the mean rain core radius, standard deviation of rain core
 316 radii, and number of rainfall events are shown in Figures 4 b, c, and d, respectively. The
 317 time axis is shifted such that time equals 0 corresponds to the time of triggering in all
 318 three simulations.

319 The first rainfall events develop 15 min after triggering in the control and weakly forced
 320 simulations, with mean radii of about 0.7 and 0.4 km, respectively. In the strongly
 321 forced simulation light precipitation commences before triggering (for the reason given in
 322 section 3.1) and rainfall events generated at triggering are larger, with a mean radius of
 323 about 1 km. After triggering, the evolution of the average radius can be divided into two
 324 stages. The growing stage characterized by a gradual growth of rain core radius extends
 325 from 0.75 to 2.75 (in the strongly forced simulation), 3 (in the control simulation), and 4
 326 (in the weakly forced simulation) hours after triggering, followed by an oscillatory stage
 327 when the mean rain core radius oscillates slowly around its equilibrium value.

328 During the growing stage, there are clear dependencies on forcing strength. The mean
 329 radius and standard deviation increase with the strength of forcing, while the number of
 330 rainfall events is relatively insensitive. The number of rainfall events increases rapidly
 331 and reaches its peak at 1.25 hours (in the control and strongly forced simulations) or
 332 1.5 hours (in the weakly forced simulation) after triggering, before decreasing rapidly to
 333 much smaller values at the end of the growing stage. The rapid reduction in the number

334 of rainfall events alongside a gradual growth of their average sizes (between $t_0 = 1.5$ – 2.5
335 hours) could suggest that smaller rainfall events disappear or else merge together to form
336 larger events.

337 During the oscillatory stage, there is no clear separations in the evolution of the mean
338 radii and standard deviation of rain core radii. The number of rainfall events continues
339 to decrease and reaches the value of zero when precipitation stops. The control and
340 strongly forced simulations generate very similar number of rainfall events from hour
341 3.25 after triggering, while the weakly forced simulations generates fewer rainfall events
342 from about hour 6 after triggering. In all three simulations the mean rain core size
343 does not vary substantially with time (compared to the number of rainfall events), away
344 from triggering. This latter result suggests that regardless of the strength of forcing the
345 evolution of convection produced by a time-varying surface forcing is mainly dominated
346 by the variability in time on the number of rainfall events, with the variability in time
347 on the rainfall characteristics (e.g., rain core size) being less important. It is consistent
348 with the result of *Davies et al.* [2013], who found that changes in mass flux are dominated
349 by changes in the number of clouds, rather than changes in the cloud size or changes in
350 strength of surface forcing.

351 **3.2.2. Memory within the convective system**

352 We now investigate how current convection depends on its own history within a given
353 area, A . For each instantaneous 2D surface precipitation field, the 512×512 (grid-scale)
354 data are average onto a $N_{Ax} \times N_{Ay}$ domain. Each area $A = N_{Ax}\Delta x \times N_{Ay}\Delta y$ on the
355 coarse-grained scale is considered to have rain present if its mean precipitation is greater
356 than 0.1 mm h^{-1} and we denote the probability of finding rain at time t_0 within some

357 area A as $P[R(A, t_0)]$. Figure 5a shows the probability of finding rain for $A = 4 \times 4 \text{ km}^2$
 358 in the control simulation. Results are the ensemble-mean over the last nine cycles and
 359 the time axis is shifted such that time equals 0 corresponds to the time of triggering. The
 360 probability of finding rain increases rapidly and reaches its maximum value at 1.75 hours
 361 after triggering, before decreasing to zero when precipitation stops.

362 The persistence of rainfall events within area A is measured in terms of the probability
 363 of finding rain at time t_0 and at an earlier time $t_0 - \Delta t$, $P[R(A, t_0) \cap R(A, t_0 - \Delta t)]$. The
 364 minimum persistence of zero is obtained if all the areas which were precipitating at time
 365 $t_0 - \Delta t$ are not precipitating at time t_0 . The maximum persistence is either $P[R(A, t_0 - \Delta t)]$
 366 if all areas which were precipitating at time $t_0 - \Delta t$ are still precipitating at time t_0 or
 367 $P[R(A, t_0)]$ if all the areas which are precipitating at time t_0 were also precipitating at
 368 time $t_0 - \Delta t$. We then evaluate the dependence of convection on its own history by
 369 comparing $P[R(A, t_0) \cap R(A, t_0 - \Delta t)]$ to the probability of finding persistent rainfall by
 370 random chance (or the expected probability given no memory). That is $P^2[R(A, t_0, \Delta t)] =$
 371 $P[R(A, t_0)] \times P[R(A, t_0 - \Delta t)]$.

372 Convection depends on its own history if $P[R(A, t_0) \cap R(A, t_0 - \Delta t)]$ is significantly
 373 different from the expected probability given no memory. A memory function that defines
 374 the influence from convection at $t_0 - \Delta t$ is defined as:

$$375 \quad \mathbf{M}(A, t_0, \Delta t) = P[R(A, t_0) \cap R(A, t_0 - \Delta t)] - P^2[R(A, t_0, \Delta t)] \quad (3)$$

376 Figure 5 b shows the evolution of the memory function during a course of a day. Results
 377 are shown for $A = 4 \times 4 \text{ km}^2$ and $t_0 = 1.5, 2, 2.25, 3.25, 5, 5.75, 6,$ and 9 hours after trig-
 378 gering. Note that the memory function is set to zero beyond time lags that corresponds to
 379 times before triggering. A positive (negative) memory implies that convection at previous

380 time $t_0 - \Delta t$ acts to enhance (suppress) convective activities at time t_0 . The minimum
381 value of \mathbf{M} represents the strongest suppressed state of convection and the transition from
382 this strongest suppressed state to the state expected given no memory (the zero line in
383 Figure 5) corresponds to the recovery time of convection. A somewhat similar memory
384 function was also considered by *Colin et al.* [2019, Section 5 of supplementary material],
385 who focused on assessing the time for the domain-mean precipitation to recover following
386 a homogenization of spatial variations.

387 In the early stage of the diurnal cycle the memory function characterizes the persistence
388 of the newly developing convection. Later in the day, the persistence of convection is
389 maintained for about an hour. An indication of local suppression is obtained for convection
390 produced from $t_0 = 2.25$ hours, suggesting that earlier convection stabilized the local area
391 and so produced a negative feedback on the subsequent development of convection within
392 the local area. From $t_0 = 2.25$ hours, the initial persistence of convection is followed by a
393 suppression for a further 1 hour (for convection produced at $t_0 = 2.25$ hours) to 2 hours
394 (for convection produced from $t_0 = 3.25$ hours) within the local areas where convection
395 where previously enhanced. The time lag at which the strongest memory occurs is slightly
396 delayed for longer t_0 . It occurs at $\Delta t = 1.25$ hours for convection produced at $t_0 = 2.25$
397 hours and at $\Delta t = 1.75$ hours for convection produced from $t_0 = 5$ hours. The memory
398 function obtained between $t_0 = 5.75$ and 7.25 hours (e.g., red curve in Figure 5 b) shows a
399 further enhancement of convection for time lags of $\Delta t = 3 - 5$ hours, suggesting that areas
400 which were less likely to rain during the previous two hours may become more favorable
401 for developing convection.

402 We investigated the sensitivity to several of the control simulation settings (not shown).
403 These memory functions are qualitatively reproduced using shorter simulations with finer
404 horizontal resolution (e.g., 100m) and using simulations on a bigger domain with coarser
405 horizontal resolution (e.g., 256×256 km with 500 m grid spacing). They are also well
406 reproduced using simulations with different radiative cooling profiles (e.g., -2 K day^{-1}
407 without additional cooling near the surface) or different initial thermodynamic profiles
408 (e.g., profiles obtained at the end of each forcing cycle). We also tested the sensitivity to
409 a smaller Bowen ratio by decreasing the peak in surface sensible heat flux while increasing
410 that in latent heat flux. The convection exhibits similar behaviour as in the control
411 simulation, and the memory functions are also very similar.

412 We now investigate the sensitivity of the memory function to the size of the area. The
413 memory function for $A = 4 \times 4 \text{ km}^2$ is compared to those obtained for $A = 0.2 \times 0.2$ (grid-
414 scale), 2×2 , 10×10 , 15×15 , 25×25 , and $50 \times 50 \text{ km}^2$. Results are shown in Figures 5
415 c and d for $t_0 = 3$ and 6 hours after triggering. During the course of the day the shapes
416 of the memory functions obtained for areas smaller than $10 \times 10 \text{ km}^2$ are qualitatively
417 similar and the strongest memory is obtained for areas between 4×4 and $10 \times 10 \text{ km}^2$
418 (Figures 5 c and d). The memory function shows a somewhat different behavior for areas
419 of $10 \times 10 \text{ km}^2$ and larger. For instance, for a $15 \times 15 \text{ km}^2$ area convection occurring at
420 $t_0 = 3$ hours (Figure 5 c) starts to recover from a time lag of $\Delta t = 2.5$ hours (time lag
421 when the memory function starts to increase from its minimum value towards the zero
422 line) compared to $\Delta t = 1.5$ hours for $A = 4 \times 4 \text{ km}^2$. However, the impact of previous
423 convection is reduced substantially for an area of $25 \times 25 \text{ km}^2$ and convective memory is
424 negligible for areas exceeding $25 \times 25 \text{ km}^2$ (e.g, $A = 50 \times 50 \text{ km}^2$). We should note that

425 the strongest memory occurs on spatial scales of very large rainfall events (Figure 4 a)
 426 while the change of behaviour of the memory function occurs on a spatial scale that is
 427 roughly the typical spacing of rain cores. For instance, for $N = 100$ the typical spacing is
 428 $\sqrt{(512 \times 0.2)^2/100} \approx 10$ km.

429 Finally, we investigate the sensitivity to the strength of forcing. Figure 6 a compares
 430 the probability of finding rain for $A = 4 \times 4$ km². The time axis is shifted such that time
 431 equals 0 corresponds to the time of triggering in all three simulations. The maximum
 432 value is reached at 1.75 hours after triggering in all three simulations. Note that the
 433 probability of finding rain is broadly equivalent to the rain area fraction and thus, the
 434 differences in the probability of finding rain between the simulations can be understood in
 435 terms of the differences in the number of rainfall events and their sizes. The probability
 436 of finding rain in the weakly forced simulation is the smallest as this simulation generates
 437 smaller rain core sizes throughout the day and fewer rainfall events from hour 6 after
 438 triggering (Figure 4). During the growing stage, the probability of finding rain in the
 439 strongly forced simulation is the greatest, suggesting that the contributions from slightly
 440 fewer and larger rainfall events exceed those from more numerous but smaller rainfall
 441 events (control simulation). During the oscillatory stage, the control and strongly forced
 442 simulations generate very similar numbers of rainfall events. However, the probability
 443 of finding rain in the strongly forced simulation remains greater because that simulation
 444 generates larger rain core sizes.

445 In all three simulations the strongest memory is obtained for areas between 4×4 and
 446 10×10 km². Figures 6 b–f compare the memory functions for $A = 4 \times 4$ km² and $t_0 = 1.5,$
 447 2, 3, 4.5, and 8 hours after triggering. The fundamental behaviour of convection in the

448 control and strongly forced simulations are similar as both simulations have qualitatively
449 similar evolution of the memory function. However, the memory function in the weakly
450 forced simulation shows a few differences. For instance, the negative memory develops a
451 little earlier in the weakly forced simulation (Figure 6 c). In addition, the appearance of
452 a secondary enhancement of precipitation occurs earlier in the diurnal cycle. It occurs
453 at $t_0 = 4.5$ hours in the weakly forced simulation (Figure 6 e) compared to $t_0 = 5.75$
454 hours in the control simulation (e.g., grey curve in Figure 5 b) and the strongly forced
455 simulation (not shown). On the other hand, the memory functions are quantitatively
456 different and the impact of previous convection increases with the strength of surface
457 forcing for convection produced from $t_0 = 7$ hours (e.g., $t_0 = 8$ hours in Figure 6 f).
458 Moreover, in all three simulations the convective memory is reduced significantly when
459 areas greater than $25 \times 25 \text{ km}^2$ are considered, and there is no convective memory for
460 $A = 50 \times 50 \text{ km}^2$.

461 These memory functions illustrate the role of previous convection in modulating current
462 convection and highlight the importance of the area of the region considered in modu-
463 lating memory effects as well as the time since triggering (t_0). The strength of forcing
464 is a secondary factor. These results suggest that for disorganised convection there is no
465 memory due to the mechanisms at play in these simulations for GCMs with grid spacings
466 coarser than 50 km. However, these memory functions are inconsistent with diagnos-
467 tic assumptions made in many current convective parameterization schemes as used in
468 numerical weather prediction models with grid spacing finer than 10 km.

4. Convective memory attributed to initial thermodynamic variability

469 Each diurnal cycle experiences the same forcing, but starts from a slightly different
470 initial state due to spatial variability. Figure 7 shows snapshots of vertical slices at
471 $y = 50$ km (a, b) and horizontal slices at heights of 1 (c, d) and 3 km (e, f) of potential
472 temperature and water vapour anomalies with respect to the domain-mean. These slices
473 are taken at 24 h of the second forcing cycle of the control simulation and they represent
474 the fluctuations in the thermodynamic fields at the start of surface forcing on the third
475 diurnal cycle. Similar magnitudes of the thermodynamic fluctuations are obtained at
476 night on the other diurnal cycles of the control simulation.

477 Below 4 km, a notable feature is the evidence of an anti-correlation between moisture
478 and temperature. For instance, there are large patches of moist (dry) anomaly of up to
479 1.2 g/kg on horizontal scales of around 40 km which are associated with a cold (warm)
480 anomaly of up to 0.4 K. Above 4 km moisture fluctuations are relatively small compared
481 to those in the lowest 4 km at 24 h. However, the potential temperature field shows more
482 significant small-scale fluctuations which are presumably associated with gravity waves
483 initiated at detrainment layers when convective cells were active, transporting heat away
484 from the convective cells. As we will show later these thermodynamic fluctuations above
485 4 km do not influence the evolution of convection on the next diurnal cycle.

486 The diurnal cycle i is thus initialized with horizontally heterogeneous thermodynamic
487 conditions generated internally via decaying deep convection from cycle $i - 1$. In order to
488 understand whether these thermodynamic fluctuations have an impact on the evolution
489 of convection on the i^{th} cycle, we perform simulations in which horizontally homogeneous
490 thermodynamic conditions (here after called “homogenization”) are imposed (without

491 changing the domain–mean state). Homogenization is applied to a thermodynamic field
 492 by relaxing that field back to its horizontal–mean.

493 Previous studies on convective memory have explored the relative importance of differ-
 494 ent prognostic variables and concluded that horizontal variations in potential temperature
 495 (θ) and water vapour mixing ratio (q_v) are the main source of convective memory [e.g.,
 496 *Stirling and Petch*, 2004; *Davies et al.*, 2013; *Colin et al.*, 2019]. We repeated the control
 497 simulation, and similarly to *Colin et al.* [2019], applied homogenization to both θ and q_v
 498 at all vertical levels between 15–24 h of the diurnal cycle $i - 1$, before allowing them to
 499 continue evolving. Here, homogenization is applied with a relaxation timescale of 1 hour
 500 and there is no thermodynamic variability left at the start of the diurnal cycle i . The cycle
 501 i will henceforth be referred to as H^{Day^i} and will be compared against the control simula-
 502 tion on the i^{th} diurnal cycle (C^{Day^i}). C^{Day^i} and H^{Day^i} start with the same domain–mean
 503 thermodynamic profiles but in contrast to C^{Day^i} , the evolution of convection in H^{Day^i} is
 504 not influenced by variability arising from the previous day.

505 Homogenization is realized nine times (for i between 2 and 10) and for each of these
 506 nine realizations the start of the simulation on the i^{th} diurnal cycle is considered to be
 507 time 0 and the ensemble–mean results are obtained by averaging the results of the nine
 508 realizations. Figure 8 compares the composite timeseries of the surface precipitation and
 509 cloud base mass flux for the control simulation and the simulations following homoge-
 510 nization. The triggering of convection occurs at the same time. However, the start of
 511 precipitation and its development are a little delayed (15 minutes) by homogenization.
 512 In addition, the domain–mean daily–mean precipitation rate is reduced by about 10%,
 513 now 0.18 mm d^{-1} compared to 0.2 mm d^{-1} in the control simulation. These results are

514 in contrast with those obtained by *Stirling and Petch* [2004] who found that the onset of
515 precipitation occurred several hours earlier and that the total rainfall amount is increased
516 by up to 70% when diurnal cycle simulations were initialized with thermodynamic fluc-
517 tuations generated from a day of deep convection. However, in contrast to this study, the
518 study of *Stirling and Petch* [2004] was conducted in 2D domain, which may enhance the
519 significance of the fluctuations on initiation. On the other hand, this study analyses the
520 impact from thermodynamic fluctuations that have decayed for 12 hours following a day
521 of deep convection and this leads to fluctuation amplitudes at least six times smaller than
522 those of *Stirling and Petch* [2004] (compare our Figure 7 with their Figure 2).

523 However, there are clear differences in the evolution of the rainfall population (Figure 9).
524 Following homogenization, the rain core size distribution is narrower and more numerous
525 and smaller rainfall events occur throughout the course of the day. The number of rainfall
526 events reaches its peak at 1.5 hours after triggering and the peak is increased by about
527 350 (about 50% increase with respect to the control simulation). Recalling also that ho-
528 mogenization reduces the rainfall amount by about 10% and that the domain-mean cloud
529 base mass flux values are very similar, convective activity associated with the individual
530 rainfall events generated in the simulations following homogenization is clearly less intense
531 (in mass flux and rainfall amount) than those generated in the control simulation.

532 Following homogenization, the more numerous rainfall events result in larger chances of
533 finding rainfall event during the first 8 hours after triggering (Figure 10 a). The strongest
534 memory is also obtained for areas between 4×4 and 10×10 km². Figures 10 b–f compare
535 the memory functions for $A = 4 \times 4$ km² and $t_0 = 1.75, 3.5, 5, 6,$ and 8 hours after
536 triggering. The variability in the initial thermodynamic fields appears to be important in

537 controlling the shape of the memory function during the course of the day. The rainfall
538 events generated following homogenization are less intense, and somewhat less persistent
539 and the negative memory and secondary enhancement develop earlier (Figure 10 c). On
540 the other hand, the local atmosphere also recovers more rapidly: up to 1.5 hours earlier
541 for convection produced between $t_0 = 2.5$ and 6.5 hours (e.g., Figure 10 c). The charac-
542 ter of these differences in the memory functions between the control simulation and the
543 simulations following homogenization are consistent across the various areas considered.

544 We further test where the important thermodynamic fluctuations occur by performing
545 additional simulations in which homogenization is restricted to the lower troposphere
546 (surface to 4 km) or to the middle and upper troposphere (4–20 km). The effects of
547 homogenization are almost zero when applied above 4 km. However, the simulations
548 following homogenization below 4 km and following homogenization at all vertical levels
549 behave very similarly. These results are consistent with those of *Stirling and Petch* [2004]
550 and *Colin et al.* [2019], who demonstrated that thermodynamic fluctuations at low levels
551 have the greatest impact on the development of convection.

5. Conclusions

552 A series of idealized high-resolution three-dimensional simulations of the diurnal cycle
553 of deep convection over land have been performed using the new Met Office NERC cloud-
554 resolving model (MONC). The simulations have features expected from diurnal cycle of
555 tropical convection. In this study convection is found to be disorganized. A memory
556 function is defined to evaluate the effects of previous convection in modifying current
557 convection. It is the difference between the probability of finding rain at time t_0 and at
558 an earlier time $t_0 - \Delta t$ and the expected probability given no memory. The shapes of the

559 memory function are similar at grey-zone scales, but there is a change in the shape at
560 spatial scales of 10 km and larger, and convective memory is reduced substantially when
561 spatial scales larger than 25 km are considered. The memory is found to be strongest at
562 grey-zone scales. In the early stage of the diurnal cycle the memory function has one phase
563 which characterizes the persistence of the newly developing convective system. Later in
564 the day, the first phase which represents the persistence of convection is maintained for
565 about an hour. There is a second phase which represents the suppression of convection
566 in regions which were raining 1 to 3 hours previously, and subsequently a third phase
567 which represents a secondary enhancement of precipitation but this is likely related to the
568 previous suppression rather than the occurrence of rainfall 3 to 6 hours ago. Each phase
569 of the memory function roughly keeps the same duration regardless of surface forcing.
570 The second and third phases are found to develop earlier for the weaker forcing, but the
571 memory function shows less sensitivity to the stronger forcing. Note that for stronger
572 forcing clouds are found to be more intense in rainfall amount and mass flux (or vertical
573 velocity) and so they are expected to be more intense in terms of the strength of the
574 associated cold pool activity. Hence, if the strength of the cold pool were driving the
575 memory we would expect the memory to depend on the intensity of those clouds and
576 so, to also depend on the strength of the forcing. The lack of dependence of convective
577 memory to the strength of forcing therefore challenges assumptions made in cold pool
578 models for memory, where the forcing for cold pool activity depends on the strength of
579 large-scale convective activity.

580 Sensitivity studies were carried out to investigate the impact of thermodynamic vari-
581 ability generated via feedback processes from previous day-time convection on the devel-

582 opment of convection on the next day. In contrast to the study of *Stirling and Petch* [2004]
583 which showed that the onset of precipitation can change by several hours and convection
584 intensity can be increased by up to 70% when simulations are initialized with convectively
585 generated thermodynamic fluctuations, our study revealed little impact on the timing of
586 convection and convection intensity is reduced by only 10% when thermodynamic fluc-
587 tuations are removed. The difference in the results is attributed to the fact that the
588 amplitudes of thermodynamic fluctuations in our study are smaller compared to those in
589 the study of *Stirling and Petch* [2004] due to their decay during the night. However, it
590 was shown that thermodynamic fluctuations do have a significant impact on the nature
591 of the rainfall events during the course of the day. Rainfall events become numerous but
592 less intense, with relatively smaller sizes when feedback of previous day–time convection
593 is excluded in the simulation of the next day. As a result, the memory function exhibits
594 more rapid decay and recovery. Additional sensitivity studies revealed that thermody-
595 namic fluctuations in the middle and upper tropospheres do not affect the evolution of
596 convection and confirmed the results of the studies of *Stirling and Petch* [2004]; *Colin*
597 *et al.* [2019] which demonstrated that convective memory attributed to thermodynamic
598 fluctuations mostly resides in the lower troposphere.

599 This study highlights the impacts of spatial thermodynamic variability on the subse-
600 quent development of convection and highlights the importance of the area of the grid
601 box, the time since triggering, and the strength of forcing in modulating memory effects
602 at grey–zone scales. The first phase of the memory function, with enhanced precipitation
603 where it was already precipitating in the past, is in principle already represented by some
604 memory mechanisms included in some convective parameterization schemes [e.g., *Willett*

605 *and Whittall, 2017*]. However, the second phase, with suppressed precipitation where it was
606 previously enhanced and the third phase, with a secondary enhancement of precipitation
607 where it was previously suppressed are not yet directly represented in convective parame-
608 terization schemes. Future studies are planned to assess the ability of current convective
609 parameterizations in capturing such effects via their feedbacks onto the resolved state.
610 This will be done by comparing the memory properties in CRM simulations, including
611 their dependencies on spatial scale and forcing strengths, against equivalent simulations
612 with GCMs.

613 These simulations represent diurnal cycle of scattered convection under very idealized
614 forcing conditions and for more realistic simulations the memory properties of convection
615 may be modified for mesoscale organized convection or by the presence of an interactive
616 land-surface; vertical wind shear; or cloud-radiative interactions. However the simula-
617 tions provide a benchmark against which to compare more complex simulations of the
618 diurnal cycle and future studies are also planned to investigate the impact of prescribed
619 heterogeneous surface conditions on the diurnal cycle of deep convection.

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Figure 1. Time–height cross sections of (a) mass flux and (b) cloud fraction. Results are shown for the components attributed to (colours) all cloudy updrafts (“ACu”) and (solid contours) buoyant cloudy updrafts (“BCu”). The mass fluxes are given per unit area. The fractional area attributed to “BCu” (or “ACu”) is calculated at each horizontal level as the sum of cloudy updrafts (or buoyant cloudy updrafts) grid points normalized by the total number of grid points. The results are obtained on the second diurnal cycle of the control simulation. For each panel the contour intervals are the same as the color bar spacing.

Figure 2. Composite timeseries of (a) precipitation, (b) cloud base mass flux and (c) cloud fraction at cloud base.

The mass flux and cloud fraction are shown for (black curves) “ACu” and (red curves) “BCu”. The mass fluxes are given per unit area. The shaded areas indicate the cycle-to-cycle fluctuations relative to the ensemble-mean value (standard deviation). Timeseries of surface forcing (sum of sensible and latent heat fluxes) scaled by (a) 10^3 , (b) 10^4 , and (c) 10^2

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are shown for reference.

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Figure 3. Composite timeseries of (a) normalized precipitation and (b) cloud base mass flux for "ACu". The normalized precipitation is defined as the instantaneous precipitation rates normalized by the domain-mean daily-mean precipitation rate. Results are shown for the (black) control simulation and for the (blue) weakly and (red) strongly forced simulations. The mass fluxes are given per unit area. The shaded areas indicate the cycle-to-cycle fluctuations relative to the ensemble-mean value (standard deviation). Timeseries of surface forcing (sum of sensible latent heat fluxes) scaled by (a) 10^3 and (b) 10^4 are shown for reference. The results on panels (a) and (b) are the same as on panels (c) and (d) but the time axis is shifted such that time equals 0 corresponds to the time of triggering in all three simulations.

Figure 4. Panel (a): Composite of PDFs of rain core area. Results are the average of PDFs between [0.25–0.75], [1–1.25], [1.5–1.75], [2–2.5], [2.75–6.5], and [6.75–9.5] hours after triggering in the control simulation. The x axis is on logarithmic scale. Panels (b), (c), and (d): Composite timeseries of (b) mean rain core radius \bar{R} , (c) standard deviation of rain core radii, σ_R , and (d) number of rainfall events N obtained in the (black) control simulation, and the (blue) weakly and (red) strongly forced simulations. The shaded areas indicate the cycle-to-cycle fluctuations relative to the ensemble mean value (standard deviation) and the time axis is shifted such that time equals 0 corresponds to the time of triggering in all three simulations.

Figure 5. (a) Probability of finding rain ($P[R(A, t_0)]$) for $A = 4 \times 4 \text{ km}^2$. The time axis is shifted such that time equals 0 corresponds to the time of triggering. (b) Memory function ($M(A, t_0, \Delta t)$) for $A = 4 \times 4 \text{ km}^2$ and $t_0 = 1.5, 2, 2.25, 3.25, 5, 6, \text{ and } 9$ hours after triggering. The memory functions for different areas are shown for $t_0 =$ (c) 3 and (d) 6 hours after triggering. Results are shown for the control simulation.

Figure 6. (a) Probability of finding rain ($P[R(A, t_0)]$) for $A = 4 \times 4 \text{ km}^2$. The time axis is shifted such that time equals 0 corresponds to the time of triggering in all three simulations. Memory function ($M(A, t_0, \Delta t)$) for $A = 4 \times 4 \text{ km}^2$ and $t_0 =$ (b) 1.5, (c) 2, (d) 3, (e) 4.5, and (f) 8 hours after triggering. Results are the ensemble-mean obtained in the (black) control simulation, and the (blue) weakly and (red) strongly forced simulations.

Figure 7. Snapshots of vertical slices at (a and b) at $y = 50$ km and horizontal slices at heights of (c and d) 1 and (e and f) 3 km of (left-hand side) potential temperature and (right-hand side) water vapour anomalies with respect to the domain mean. Results are taken at 24 h of the second forcing cycle of the control simulation.

Figure 8. As in Figures 2 a and b but for the (black) control simulation and (red) the simulations following homogenization of θ and q_v at all vertical levels. The cloud base mass flux are shown for “ACu”.

Figure 9. As in Figures 4 b, c, and d but for the (black) control simulation and (red) the simulations following homogenization of θ and q_v at all vertical levels. The time axis is shifted such that time equals 0 corresponds to the time of triggering.

Figure 10. (a) Probability of finding rain ($P[R(A, t_0)]$) for $A = 4 \times 4 \text{ km}^2$. The time axis is shifted such that time equals 0 corresponds to the time of triggering in both cases. Memory function ($M(A, t_0, \Delta t)$) for $A = 4 \times 4 \text{ km}^2$ and $t_0 =$ (b) 1.75, (c) 3.5, (d) 5, (e) 6, and (f) 8 hours after triggering. Results are the ensemble-mean of the (black) control simulation, and the (red) simulations following homogenization of θ and q_v at all vertical levels.